

Biological Resources Certifications Schemes

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Authors

Name	Organisation	Email
Duřica Banduka	nova-Institut GmbH	Dusica.banduka@nova-institut.de
Dr. Anke Schwarzenberger	nova-Institut GmbH	Anke.schwarzenberger@nova-institut.de

Type

- R** Document report
- DEM** Demonstrator, pilot, prototype
- DEC** Websites, patent fillings, videos, etc.
- OTHER**

Dissemination Level

- PU** Public, fully open, e.g. web
- SEN** Sensitive, limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement
- CI** Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 1001/844/EC

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Internal reviewer(s)

Name	Organisation	Email
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Publishable Executive Summary

BioReCer aims to ensure the environmental performance and traceability of biological feedstock used by the bio-based industries. This will be executed through the deployment of guidelines to strengthen current certification schemes by including new criteria that align with EU taxonomy and EU corporate due diligence regulations. Within this approach, the added value, the use, as well as the social acceptance of bioproducts will be increased. With this objective in mind, BioReCer is structured in three main technological pillars:

- 1) development of a multidimensional assessment framework and a digital BioReCer ICT-tool (BIT) for the aggregated and collaborative analysis of biological feedstocks and their associated supply chains;
- 2) creation of a BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living-Lab (BRIE-LL) following a multi-agent approach and the testing of this framework in four bio-based supply chain case studies,
- 3) using all generated knowledge to complement current certification schemes by including new sustainability and traceability criteria, and ensure their applicability at EU and global scale.

The transition to a bio-based economy is expected to deliver substantial environmental, societal and economic benefits. For this, BioReCer will assess the impact of current and adapted certification schemes on (end-)users and bio-based industries stakeholders' willingness to pay (WTP) along with acceptance of new bio-value chains from biological feedstocks, including residual feedstock and waste, by industries and consumers. The project will design and develop a multidimensional assessment framework to analyse the environmental performance of biological resources and traceability. This framework will be subsequently validated in 4 full bio-based systems which will allow for the applicability in a wide range of bio-based value chains. This approach will be unfolded by the joint creation of two levels of interaction: a physical one through the creation of a BioResources Stakeholders Platform (BRSP) and a "digital" one through a BioReCer ICT tool (BIT).

The BioReCer communication and dissemination strategy aims to maximise the project-impact through addressing and including relevant stakeholder and target groups via suitable channels and instruments combined in a cohesive strategy.

This document is the first version of the communication and dissemination plan **D8.1**, which acts as a living document and will be updated on a regular basis in M18, M24 and M36.

1 Communication and Dissemination Plan

The Communication and Dissemination Plan (CDP) presents a strategy to impactfully address identified stakeholder and target groups. The communication and dissemination plan includes activities, channels and instruments for communication and dissemination that the consortium will use in order to ensure high visibility, information accessibility and effective promotion of the project and generated results throughout the entire project duration. In this context, the CDP will serve as a guideline and reference framework to guide and evaluate the impact of communication and dissemination activities that have been carried out. This will be achieved by identifying suitable key performance indicators (KPIs). Should the taken measures fail to meet the defined communication and dissemination goals, the plan will introduce alternative paths and solutions. The CDP will be continuously updated and adjusted with progressing project status and will inform about the executed measures.

1.1 Objectives of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

Key objective of the communication and dissemination strategy presented in this plan is to ensure an adequate communication of project objectives and results to relevant stakeholders and the broad public, while at the same time supporting an effective dissemination of generated knowledge (e.g. methods, results). It covers task **T8.1** of the BioReCer project. The continuous management and coordination of planned and executed communication and dissemination activities will ensure that the project impact is maximised on economic, scientific, environmental and societal level, and generated results are exploited in the best possible way.

The presented document aims to realise the project objectives in order to:

- Invite different stakeholder groups to participate in the BRSP and contribute to the success of BioReCer;
- Increase the public's sensitivity and information towards the tackled challenges within BioReCer and developed solutions;
- Inform producers of residuals, biowaste and waste disposal contractors, sellers, distributors, bio-based industries and retailers about the potential value of waste and the tracking and traceability of associated value-chains thus opening up new businesses;
- Raise awareness towards sustainable value chains and valuable renewable products from waste and residues, and communicate the approach and outputs from BioReCer to consumers and the general public;
- Present guidelines for certification schemes established by the BioReCer project to policy-makers and certification bodies in order to adapt and strengthen current certification schemes to incorporate bio-based/waste-based value chains;
- Enable and encourage other researchers to exploit results through further research, development and action;

- Encourage students and young researchers to consider participation in science and technology and anticipate the generated knowledge in their own efforts (and also to increase the number of women and non-binary scientists in this sector);
- Support policy makers, NGOs and authorities in their decision-making process and hereby optimise the political framework for the effective establishment of sustainable solutions in order to motivate investments and lower potential investor risks;
- Promote the goals of the wider Horizon Europe work programme of the EU towards a climate neutral Europe.

Communication and dissemination activities will therefore include:

- A stakeholder analysis, following the results of the comprehensive stakeholder and target group analysis executed in WP2 and WP3 that will be used for the set-up and coordination of the BRSP in WP4 in tasks **T4.1** and **T4.2** for deliverables **D4.1** and **D4.4** respectively,
- Provision of tailor-made communication and dissemination solutions for various stakeholder and target groups through suitable channels, mediums and tools,
- A modern and distinct project identity with related materials (logo, templates for Word, PowerPoint),
- A project website,
- A protected Google Drive for secure internal document exchange,
- Publishable physical and digital marketing materials (brochures, flyers, rollups),
- At least two policy briefs,
- A project video,
- Frequent press releases (at least three),
- Publications in popular press and relevant trade magazines,
- Continuous and growing social media presence,
- Presentations and participation at relevant conferences and trade fairs to inform the bio-based industry and the scientific community,
- Stakeholder workshops (webinars and in person trainings),
- Open access scientific publications in peer reviewed journals, book chapters and conference proceedings,
- Dissemination through Horizon Europe Instruments (Horizon Results Platform, The Horizon Europe Innovation Radar and the Horizon Magazine).

Effective communication and dissemination will be secured and monitored through:

- Identifying suitable KPIs and methods to assess executed communication and dissemination activities to ensure an effective reach of the defined target and stakeholder groups (e.g., by using website statistics or tracking and analytical tools),
- Conveying clear and cohesive project messages,
- Documentation of activities, evaluation of their efficiency and suitable adaptation of the strategy to increase the impact of communication and dissemination activities.

1.2 Definitions of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation

BioReCer is a multidisciplinary project that includes partners from different industries and sectors while at the same time addressing a multitude of different stakeholder and target

groups. Tailor made communication, dissemination and exploitation strategies therefore are crucial to accelerate the application success of the developed certification schemes and related instruments. They will further raise awareness, increase acceptance and present generated research results and innovation actions of BioReCer to the scientific community, the bio-based industry, policy makers and the broad public. This will be achieved through an effective internal and external transfer of knowledge and information.

The elements and related actions of communication, dissemination and exploitation represent highly interlinked activities that support and complement each other in order to maximise the multi-perspective project impact. Yet, all three elements serve different purposes, address different stakeholder and target groups and thus use different instruments. The differences and purposes of these single elements are explained in the following.

Communication activities serve the purpose to introduce the project to relevant stakeholder groups, the media as well as the broad public and inform about the project objectives, progress, results and related activities. This is executed through strategic and targeted promotion and information measures addressing a multitude of audiences and conveying clear messages. Communication measures aim at creating interactive exchange between project partners, relevant stakeholders and society through steadily ensuring and increasing stakeholder engagement and sensitivity towards project related issues. Hereby, stakeholder awareness and acceptance of the developed schemes and tools for bio-based feedstock is increased. Effective communication is ensured through the choice of suitable communication channels (such as press releases, social media and digital networks and the project website). Transparent and continuous communication activities demonstrate how EU-funded projects contribute to tackle societal and environmental challenges and that taxpayer money is spent consciously and in a beneficial way in order to develop and introduce impactful positive solutions.

Dissemination activities present an essential element of good research practices by circulating knowledge and making project results publicly available free of charge to any interested stakeholder group, e.g. through Open Access and FAIR science. A focus is set on the scientific and academic community and certification and standardisation bodies that can best make use of project results through future research and implementation. The dissemination strategy therefore focuses on approaches of open access publishing, e.g. in the form of scientific publications in journals, presentations at (scientific) conferences or related fairs, publications in conference proceedings as well as the creation of and contribution to suitable open access databases. Additional media will increase the original focus-radius of the generated results and support the transfer and diffusion of generated knowledge into related but also alternative scientific disciplines. The overarching goal of all dissemination activities is to maximise the impact of generated results, support future research and make scientific results a common good.

Exploitation describes the process of making concrete use of generated results in commercial, societal and political purposes by identifying exploitable results and respective stakeholder groups. This is executed e.g. by improving public knowledge, application and transferring it into a supportive political framework. This includes stakeholder groups like researchers, policy makers, certification bodies, holders of certification schemes, industrial bodies, specifically SMEs, entrepreneurs and the civil society. The results can be exploited by developing, creating and marketing a product or process, by creating and providing a service, by the standardisation of activities or supporting the design of beneficial political frameworks and instruments. The project partners can exploit results themselves or facilitate exploitation through others, e.g. by making results available under open license agreements.

1.3 Communication and Dissemination Tasks and Deliverables

The BioReCer WP8 Communication and Dissemination includes the following deliverables and related tasks, which will be executed throughout the project duration in order to maximise the project impact on a multi-perspective level.

Table 1: Overview BioReCer WP8 Tasks

No.	Task-Title	Lead	Due Date/Time
T8.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	NOVA	0-6
T8.2	Dissemination Activities	NOVA	1-36
T8.2.1	Publications (Scientific articles and informative material)	NOVA	1-36
T8.2.2	Project presence at relevant scientific conferences and events	NOVA	1-36
T8.2.3	Workshops for training actions and user testing	NOVA	1-36
T8.3	Communication Activities	NOVA	1-36
T8.3.1	Corporate Identity of the project	NOVA	6
T8.3.2	Project website and display of project outcomes	NOVA	1-36
T8.3.3	Leaflet on the project, roll-up banners, infographics, posters, project video.	NOVA	1-36
T8.3.4	Social Media Activity	NOVA	1-36

T8.3.5	Content calendar, tracker and KPIs	NOVA	1-36
T8.3.6	Newsletter and Press Releases	NOVA	1-36

The listed tasks will result in the following deliverables to be executed and provided by the named partners.

Table 2: Overview BioReCer Deliverables

No.	Title	Lead	Form	Dis. Level	Due Date
D8.1	Communication and Dissemination Plan	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	6
D8.2	Project Website	NOVA	DEC – websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	6
D8.3	Project Leaflet	NOVA	DEC – websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	6
D8.4	Project Video	NOVA	DEC – websites, patent filings, videos, etc.	PU – Public	18
D8.5	Mid Report on BioReCer Communication Activities	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	18
D8.6	First Policy Brief	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	18
D8.7	Final Report on BioReCer Communication Activities	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	36
D8.8	Final Policy Brief	NOVA	R – Document, Report	PU – Public	36

The tasks and associated deliverables will further cover Milestone 10 (**M10**), which includes the realisation of the project website, an internal communication platform (i.e. Google Drive), a newsletter and a leaflet. The lead beneficiary of milestone 10 is NOVA, with M10 being due in project month 6.

1.4 Communication and Dissemination of Expected Impacts and Core Messages

The BioReCer communication and dissemination plan covers task **T8.1** and follows the objective to generate and realise the greatest possible impact for information, results and knowledge generated within the BioReCer project on multiple levels (economic, environmental, scientific, societal). Therefore, the BioReCer communication and dissemination strategy foresees tailor-made activities for all identified stakeholder and target groups. The communication and dissemination task leader will create, apply, analyse and eventually modify suitable and effective instruments and channels. These will allow BioReCer to respond flexibly to aberrations of the specific work packages, emerging risks or in case of deviation to the initially expected outcomes to establish and take suitable corrective measures. The deviations will be identified based on KPIs.

The dissemination and communication strategy of BioReCer addresses the following impact areas:

- **Economic/Technological:** BioReCer will enhance tracking and traceability of bio-based feedstock and hereby increase market value for stakeholders along the value-chains of bio-based economies. It will create new and strengthen established markets for bio-based feedstock and related products. These markets will support the European bioeconomy as well as its competitiveness and productivity.
- **Scientific:** Generate reliable knowledge on certification and labelling indicators for the bio-based industries, provide a promising information and knowledge basis to encourage and enable future research in the field of renewable, bio-based materials and feedstocks, related value chains and industries as well as renewable carbon by respecting and supporting an Open Access and FAIR science approach. Whenever possible, data and generated knowledge will be published in open access repositories and the project website.
- **Environmental:** Introduce and provide available and effective tools and instruments (i.e. reliable circular indicators, BRSP, BRIE-LL, BIT) which will foster bio-based feedstocks and related industries and support the progress towards defossilisation of the industry by substituting fossil-based resources with renewable bio-based alternatives. Furthermore, these tools and instruments will present solutions to lower CO₂-emissions, increase transparency and acceptance of bio-based feedstocks, related products and materials and their associated value chains.
- **Societal:** By targeting end-consumers, consumer agencies as well as the press and media, BioReCer will raise awareness and sensitivity towards climate and environmental issues, draw attention to currently available sustainable innovative and bio-based solutions and their value chains as well as related consumer goods. For this, BioReCer will identify relevant factors and terminologies to increase societal acceptance of the developed technology and products, increase general societal engagement, create new jobs in the bio-based economy and wastewater sector and related industries. BioReCer will further display and communicate that taxpayer money is spent in a meaningful, beneficial and impactful way.

Through a multitude of harmonised communication and dissemination activities, BioReCer aims at realising the following defined impacts:

- 1) Assess, create and strengthen EU certification and labelling schemes by increasing transparency, and tracking and traceability of bio-based feedstocks,
- 2) Create effective, innovative, green and digitalised ways to use sustainable solutions for the bio-based industries, related feedstocks, produced goods and value chains,
- 3) Increase market uptake of green, bio-based solutions (including waste) based on less intensive resource consumption,
- 4) Contribute to a climate neutral, circular bio-based economy and hereby support the goals of the EU green deal,
- 5) Provide and establish bio-based feedstock solutions to replace fossil-based raw materials with high-performance bio-based alternatives and decrease dependency on fossil imports,
- 6) Increase productivity, innovation capacity, resilience, sustainability, and global competitiveness of the European bioeconomy.

The communication and dissemination plan aims to communicate the following identified core messages:

Table 3: WP-Titles and Core-Messages

WP	WP-Title	Core-Message	Stakeholder/ Target Group
WP1	Project Management	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ensure the delivery of the project on time and on budget, to guarantee an effective and efficient progress; deal with administrative and financial management of the project; continuously evaluate and monitor the technical/impact content of the project; secure consistent high quality of the work to be performed; manage risks and issues effectively; ensure the overall legal, contractual and ethical management of the project. 	BioReCer project partners, European Commission, tax payers
WP2	Environmental Sustainability Assessment: Diagnosis and Mapping of Current Indicators and Data Collection of Biological Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> map the main biological feedstock flows for industrial bio-based systems; identify the environmental and circularity criteria to be included in bio-based certification schemes; develop environmental impact and circularity assessment methodologies for bio-based feedstock. 	Producers of biowaste, waste disposal contractors, sellers, distributors, bio-based industries and retailers
WP3	Product Tracking and Traceability (T&T) for Circular Value Chain Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> create the T&T framework and relevant digital technologies to monitor the flow of biological feedstock throughout the supply chain; develop the necessary information to facilitate evaluation-correlations between certification criteria and end products resulting in digital passports and certification. 	BRIE-LL, BRSP, certification schemes and policy makers
WP4	Integration of the Environmental and Traceability Assessment Framework into Established Certification Schemes	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> design and set-up a bio-based multi-stakeholder platform to discuss concerns and capture feedback; test and evaluate the integration of the assessment framework into bio-based certification schemes. 	Producers of biowaste, waste disposal contractors, sellers, distributors, bio-based industries and retailers, certification bodies, policy makers
WP5	BioReCer Information and communication technologies (ICT) Tool	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> turn knowledge and the Environmental and Circularity Assessment Framework into a web-based Data Support System (DSS); propose the ICT tool to all stakeholders and public bodies to be used for exploring multiple sustainability assessment alternatives for the biological feedstocks; 	BRSP

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> technically prepare the platform to fit traceability requirements of a certification scheme. 	
WP6	Demonstration of the Developed Methodologies on the four Case Studies and Study of Replicability/ Transferability	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> establish a framework according agile value-based innovation methods to connect technical WPs; ensure applicability of the model in strategic sectors related to production and trade of biological resources; analyse the potential replicability and transferability of the model in other main European biomass flows. 	BRSP
WP7	Exploitation Plan	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> maximise the project impact amongst all the bioresources stakeholders at international level; define commercial interest on the Key Exploitation Results (KERs) and analyse the solutions viability; prepare an exploitation plan and a specific strategy in compliance with regulations; develop a strategic roadmap for standardisation. 	Scientific community, producers of biowaste and waste disposal contractors, sellers, distributors, bio-based industries and retailers
WP8	Communication and Dissemination	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> position the BioReCer project as an international reference in terms of certification schemes for sustainability; promote and boost the relations of BioReCer partners with the bio-based value chain stakeholders and the public and private institutions related to it, including the stakeholder network entities; raise awareness amongst the different target audiences; communicate the activity developed by BioReCer and the support provided by the Horizon EU to the society. 	All stakeholder groups including the general public

1.5 Stakeholder Analysis

Due to its inclusive and interactive stakeholder approach, the BioReCer project relies on a comprehensive stakeholder analysis. While detailed stakeholder identification and analysis are a focus point in **WP2** and **WP4**, as well as stakeholders identified in the case studies of **WP6**, communication and dissemination efforts will also address specific stakeholder groups through effective channels and instruments.

The planned activities will therefore address the following stakeholder groups.

Table 4: Identified BioReCer Stakeholder Groups

Stakeholder-Group	Specifics and C&D Goals
Producers of Biological Resources	BioReCer tools and guidelines will ensure the traceability, safety and environmental sustainability of the biological resources, by generating greater visibility and transparency for consumers. C&D activities will communicate the opportunities created through BioReCer tools, address potential barriers and solutions to minimise risks. They further will take effort to lower information asymmetries and strengthen the up-take, position and performance of biological resources in various industrial markets. This stakeholder group includes any producer of biological resources with specific focus on the case-study industries, i.e. agriculture, forestry and pulp industry, fishing and waste and wastewater treatment facilities.
Bio-based Industries, Traders, Distributors, Retailers	BioReCer will ensure and improve the traceability of biological resources in different value chains. C&D activities will communicate the added value of taking up bio-based resources as well as resources based on waste and wastewater, and communicate the benefits of developed schemes, labels and BioReCer tools, while reducing information asymmetries and risks.
Certification and Standardisation Bodies	BioReCer will provide effective tools to analyse and certify the traceability and sustainability of bioresources in bio-based value chains and communicate the created added value of the renewed certification and labelling schemes. Due to their executive position this group will be a major target of C&D activities.
Scientific Community	In BioReCer, generated output will foster synergies with other research organisations and research projects. Enabling knowledge transfer, information availability and the stimulation of additional future research therefore are focus points of C&D efforts. This will be achieved through interactive communication and exchange as well as by following Open Access and FAIR science.
Institutions and Policy Makers	BioReCer aims at influencing, shaping and optimising the political framework conditions through policy briefs, recommendations and practical suggestions.
General Public, Consumer Organisations and Agencies, Media	BioReCer aims at increasing consumer and general societal sensitivity for environmental issues and challenges of the bio-based industries, at increasing acceptance for developed solutions and displaying that tax-payer money is spent in a responsible, impactful and meaningful way.

2 Communication and Dissemination

2.1 Project Identity

In order to present BioReCer and its results in a modern, appealing and cohesive way and increase its recognition, the project received a current, modern and clear project identity. This identity covers task **T8.3.1** and shapes all internal and external communication and dissemination channels and related materials. The project identity includes a project logo and related graphic identity, i.e., a specific colour scheme, templates for Microsoft PowerPoint and Microsoft Word for deliverables, reports and milestones, a website design, templates for non-scientific publications as well as material for online and offline communication such as (digital) banners, posters, brochures, flyers and roll-up banners. A cohesive and recognisable project identity ensures consistency in all publishable marketing materials. The created communication and dissemination material will be used at various occasions (e.g. conferences, fairs, science exhibitions) to communicate the project objectives and aspired benefits to various stakeholder groups and raise awareness for the challenges tackled within the BioReCer project. These measures will increase stakeholder engagement and acceptance of developed solutions and applications, and their related industries. A branded project identity ensures that all project related material conveys a cohesive and consistent message within internal and external communication and dissemination paths. The graphic identity and material were created with joint input from the entire project consortium.

nova-Institute provided a first set of logo suggestions (based on a survey among the project partners on colours and associations with the term "BioReCer") for which the consortium voted for in-person and online during the first face-to-face meeting.

Figure 1: Logo suggestions by nova-Institute

Following the voting results, logo suggestions 3 and 5 (Fig. 1) were developed further into a new set of logos by incorporating feedback and relevant aspects mentioned by the consortium. One of these requests included various colours to incorporate and resemble the four different waste-streams covered by the four case studies within BioReCer. The voting was held online and included the following suggestions (Fig. 2 and 3).

Figure 2: Variations Logo Design One

Figure 3: Variations Logo Design Two

Which is your preferred logo design?

Answered: 36 Skipped: 0

Figure 4: Logo Voting Results

Using the online voting tool SurveyMonkey, participants chose version c) of design two (Fig. 3) as their preferred logo (Fig. 4). A separate voting was held to select the notation and position of the project acronym and resulted in the notation “BioReCer” positioned on the right side of the logo.

The final logo design was created based on these voting results. Various sizes of the project logo and the defined colour codes are available in the annex of this document. The logo icon represents the four bio-based value chains investigated in the four BioReCer case studies 1) wastewater and waste of the fish canning industry (blue), 2) municipal waste and wastewater (grey), 3) agricultural waste (yellow), and 4) forestry waste (green), while the circular spiral hints at the overarching goal of realising a circular economy.

Figure 5: BioReCer Final Logo Design

Based on the selected logo and colour scheme, nova-Institute created templates for reporting, deliverables, milestones and presentations. These will increase and support the external recognition of BioReCer and ensure a cohesive project representation.

Figure 6: BioReCer PowerPoint and Deliverable Templates

2.2 Internal Communication

Regular internal communication between the consortium partners forms the basis for any effective and impactful dissemination and exploitation of the project results. To create maximum internal and external involvement, all BioReCer partners are and will be involved in various communication and dissemination activities. Therefore, all partners will advise and report on project related issues, generated results, the communication and

dissemination strategy as well as the optimisation of applicability and exploitation of the technological and scientific project results.

It is crucial that all partners receive the information and (intermediate) results they need in order to conduct and perform their individual tasks in the best possible way. Effective internal communication within the project and interactive exchange between project partners therefore presents priorities and will be extended to external stakeholders in the future process of the project.

To allow an easy exchange of documents and relevant information, an internal and firewall protected Google Drive was established. The drive is hosted by the project coordinator Cetaqua but provides access to all participating project partners. The drive includes templates, reporting materials as well as joint and finalised documents.

To make sure all participating partners are provided with sufficient information and notified in time, Cetaqua created contact lists that were shared with all partners. These include 1) a contact list covering contact person information from each partner and their responsibilities within the project (e.g. technical, financial and administrative topics); 2) a general contact list with all participants in the project. The latter one can be sorted by work package and allows easy communication with respective persons involved in the specific work packages.

Work package leaders will communicate, coordinate and circulate any relevant information, document, plan and deliverable connected to their specific work package among all of its members. If required and relevant, the executive board is to be included.

The work package leaders will further deliver progress reports and related project documentations, which also includes reporting and reports on executed communication and dissemination activities. The communication and dissemination task is led by nova-Institute, who will organise the internal communication and external communication and dissemination via several activities and tools and will monitor the progress on different communication and dissemination topics every six months. Internal notification procedures and EU regulations for correct external communication, dissemination and outside appearance of the project are explained below in more detail.

2.2.1 Dissemination Notification Procedures

During the project and for a period of one year after the end of the project, any dissemination of own results by one or several parties including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of **Article 17** of the Grant Agreement and its Annex Section Dissemination, subject to the following provisions: A party shall not include in any dissemination activity another party's results or background without obtaining the owning party's prior written approval, unless they are already published.

Prior notice of any planned publication or presentation shall be given to the other parties at least 15 calendar days before the intended and indicated publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing

to the coordinator and to the party or parties proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

Before the planned publication all project partners will be notified by email through an Advance Notice Text, which includes:

- an attachment of the full (pre)publication or at least the abstract including title, author(s), and partners involved;
- where and when the publication will be submitted to or at which event it will be presented.
- Project partners may object if they can show that their protection of results would be adversely affected by the publication, their legitimate interests in relation to the publication would be significantly harmed, or their confidential information would become public, if the disclosure is permitted.

Any other beneficiary may object within 15 days of receiving notification, if it can show that its legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed. In such cases, the results may not be disseminated unless appropriate steps are taken to safeguard those interests. If no objection is received, the publication is permitted. Objections are justified if:

- a. the protection of the objecting party's results or background would be adversely affected;
- b. the objecting party's legitimate interests in relation to the results or background would be significantly harmed, or;
- c. the proposed publication includes confidential information of the objecting party.

Partners should submit any justified objections, with precise modification instructions, to [main beneficiary email] and the project coordinator within 15 days after receiving notification.

If an objection has been raised, the involved parties shall discuss how to overcome the justified grounds for the objection on a timely basis (for example by amendment to the planned publication and/or by protecting information before publication) and the objecting party shall not unreasonably continue the opposition if appropriate measures are taken following the discussion.

The objecting party can request a publication delay of not more than 90 calendar days from the time it raises such an objection. After 90 calendar days the publication is permitted, provided that confidential information of the objecting party has been removed from the publication as indicated by the objecting party.

Once partners have completed the publishing requirements, please inform the project consortium about:

- Title
- Author(s)
- Place of publication + issue no. or volume
- Year of publication
- Provide an according link

- Information whether you used green or gold open access
- If green open access, what embargo period was agreed on? (max. 6 months)
- Publication costs (needed for report, eligible for reimbursement)
- ISSN number
- DOI (if there is one, otherwise a new DOI will be created via Zenodo)

Details on Open Access publication paths are explained in the specific chapter of this document.

2.2.2 Meetings

Internal communication will further be executed in the form of regular in-person and online project meetings. More details on meeting procedures, scheduled meetings and meeting etiquette are listed in deliverable **D1.1 Project Management Plan**.

2.2.3 Data Management and FAIR Science

The internal consortium's Google Drive will help to store, share and co-edit digital files and procedures in a monitored co-operative way. It hereby provides an easy solution for the sharing and handling of sensitive information between partners as a crucial part of secure collaboration within the project. In order to execute their tasks, all partners must have sufficient access to information and data.

All project partners must manage the digital research data generated within the action responsibly and in line with the FAIR principles. These will secure the 'findability', 'accessibility', 'interoperability' and 're-usability' of data and information and hereby maximise the project's impact. Partners therefore must deposit and ensure open access to the deposited data to BioReCer partners and to the European Commission for verification purposes (if required). Whenever possible and confidentiality agreements are not compromised, generated data will be made accessible for the public. The data management lead will be responsible for quality assurance and making BioReCer project data FAIR.

Metadata of deposited publications must be open under a Creative Common Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent, in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-readable and machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following:

- publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue);
- Horizon Europe funding;
- grant number, project name and acronym;
- licensing terms;
- persistent identifiers such as the DOI of the publication,
- authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.
- Where applicable, metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

If necessary for the realisation of the project, license free access to background and foreground will be provided to all participants of the network. For further research and exploitation rights beyond the project, the consortium declares to provide each of the participants access to results and technology on reasonable conditions.

Nightly backup and replication into multiple copies in the online system will be performed for the safe storage of data. The long-term preservation strategy will ensure that the tools, as well as the primary qualitative and quantitative data produced throughout the project can be found, understood, accessed, and used for at least ten years after the project completion.

Publishable data will be transferred to the Zenodo online repository, which will ensure sustainable archiving of the final research data. Items deposited in Zenodo will be retained for the lifetime of the repository. Zenodo is hosted by CERN within the framework of the European Commission's OPENAir framework.

More information on data handling and IP processing are provided in deliverable **D1.2 Open Science and Data Management Plan (DMP)** which includes the guidelines on how to make shared data findable, accessible, interoperable and re-usable (FAIR). The Data Management Plan serves as a living document and will be annually updated during the runtime of the project.

2.2.4 Transparency and Accountability

All conducted research should propose design improvements for media that can effectively increase the transparency and accountability of media and contribute to reinvigorating a democratic scientific approach. The communication and dissemination strategy of BioReCer will therefore be guided by the transparency and accountability principles and strategy of The Horizon Europe Programme. Dissemination and communication will take place during the entire project runtime through a multitude of activities by all partners. These include the website and the social media web portals (Twitter and LinkedIn), press releases as well as publications. Furthermore, all project related events and the collaboration of multipliers and stakeholders within the project will support the idea of transparency and accountability. The project is committed to inform the consortium and the public about progress, financial status and generated results, which among other paths will be realised through continuous reporting and accessible information on the EU CORDIS website of the BioReCer project, assessable via <https://cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101060684>.

2.2.5 Gender, Equality and Diversity

Equality between women, non-binary persons and men in research and development is an essential condition for the optimum development of Horizon Europe efforts. BioReCer will actively take measures to promote equal opportunity and support equal participation of women, non-binary persons and men in line with the gender equality plans wherever applicable.

Sex and gender will be addressed as a variable during project execution for those tasks in which it may influence the pursued outcome such as the societal perception and acceptance studies, and promotion/communication material. This will also apply to aspects like human rights, working conditions or cultural heritage with many different sub-indicators.

The participating partners will share relevant gender and diversity aspects within the positioning and publishing of their results with the consortium. Where relevant, gender-neutral result positioning will be pursued, this specifically includes marketing efforts and consumer studies. Furthermore, BioReCer aims at a balanced representation of women in any stakeholder and end-user focus groups activity addressed and executed throughout the project.

Aspects of cultural and racial diversity will also be a focus of all created communication and dissemination material and display people with different backgrounds, physical features and gender to ensure an appropriate representation of the broad society.

In addition, all documents created in BioReCer will use non-discriminatory and inclusive language. This includes hashtags that should disentangle the separate compound words with uppercase letters, e.g. **#BioResource**, in order to make them readable for dyslectic persons. All research results will be disseminated and communicated in a transparent, fair and unbiased way with respect for colleagues, research participants, society, ecosystems, cultural heritage and the environment. All partners but especially women and non-binary persons from the consortium will be encouraged to disseminate generated project results through participation and representation at conferences, courses, classes and other measures. This approach will further transfer to all forms of external communication and activities.

An in-depth overview of the ethical commitments of BioReCer is provided in deliverable **D1.3 Legal and ethical project guidelines (EPG)**.

2.3 External Communication and Dissemination

In order to maximise impact, the BioReCer communication and dissemination strategy is based on an extensive stakeholder analysis (see **WP2** and **WP3**), which will effectively target different stakeholder groups through suitable channels, hereby considering their variety in expertise, background and interest. Communication activities will ensure that the project objectives, structure and progress are communicated to the identified stakeholder groups and the broad public, while dissemination efforts will support the sufficient diffusion of results and knowledge through suitable dissemination instruments in order to maximise the project impact (scientific, economic, environmental, societal).

All external communication and dissemination activities will follow the objectives listed in section **1.1** of this document.

Besides actively utilising offered EC communication and dissemination routes (CORDIS, EU horizon magazine), dissemination and communication activities will include a variety of

channels and tools for the external communication and dissemination of BioReCer in order to address the identified groups in the most effective way as well as tailor-made instruments developed in the project.

2.3.1 Online Activities

Website

The URL for the BioReCer website was reserved and established in the first project weeks under www.biorecer.eu. The website represents deliverable **D8.2** and is hosted and maintained by nova-Institute in coordination with project lead Cetaqua and supportive input from the entire project consortium. It provides a quick overview of the project objectives and aspired solutions, addressed challenges, related work packages and case studies. It will further inform about the contributing partners and communicate project news, progress and events to interested stakeholders and the broad public while also offering access to project results, public deliverables and project related publications.

The website serves as the main communication and dissemination tool for BioReCer-related information and results. A contact form will offer interested parties the opportunity to submit an application as a stakeholder for the BRSP. Also, a registration form for the BioReCer newsletter is available. The website will be continuously updated with new information in the form of scientific publications, public deliverables, press releases, scientific schooling material and promotional material. It will further provide access to digital media contributions, e.g., project videos, and be used for the promotion of BioReCer related events such as fairs, conferences, stakeholder workshops and webinars. This includes the promotion of the stakeholder workshops that represent **Task T8.2.3** "Workshops for Training Actions/User Testing" and establishes links to related deliverables **D8.1, D8.6 and D8.8**. Furthermore, the website will be used for execution of at least one interactive quiz.

The website will include a dedicated publications and public deliverables section that will make any presented material and published material available for download and hereby support the framework of Open Access Publication and FAIR Science. This equals task **T8.3.2**. This publications and public deliverables section includes any publication that does not compromise confidentiality agreements or sensitive information, i.e. conference proceedings, scientific publications and deliverables classified as public. It hereby also serves as a dissemination tool for results generated within the BioReCer project and ensures a sufficient diffusion of knowledge and information into the scientific community and specific stakeholder groups.

In order to utilise synergies and networks with related projects, a dedicated cluster section on a subpage will be created in the future.

The website performance will be continuously monitored by the analytics tool "Matomo LogFile Analytics", which provides a multitude of useful information about visitor statistics, visit durations and visitor locations. These analyses will serve as a basis for continuous

improvement and optimisation of the chosen measures and presented content of the project website.

All website activities will be accompanied and promoted by additional communication and dissemination activities, e.g. Social Media postings (LinkedIn and Twitter) of news, events, available publications, project videos, newsletters, press releases or publications in professional magazines. Social Media activities using the hashtag **#BioReCer** will also be displayed in an integrated Social Media Feed on the website, keeping visitors informed about BioReCer related social media news.

The website will be continuously up-dated and maintained throughout the project duration and 5 years after the project's completion.

Social Media and nova-Network

With regard to the continuously increasing relevance of digital communication, social media platforms represent important channels for the sharing and communication of relevant project-related content as well as for the dissemination of project results to specific target groups. Social media and social media groups allow to reach out to a broad audience of various stakeholder groups, while also addressing specialised groups with high interest in specific topics. Especially the social media platforms LinkedIn and Twitter feature (regional) groups on a wide variety of interests that allow them to reach specific target groups with high engagement. Social Media activities cover task **T8.3.3** of the BioReCer project.

LinkedIn

Due to its strong network character, the platform LinkedIn has established itself as an effective tool for communication of project-related information. A majority of the consortium partners own well connected LinkedIn profiles with broad professional networks. This includes personal profiles of participating project members and accounts of their affiliated enterprises. Many project partners have further joined specific interest groups within this very well-established social media business platform, that allow the communication of target specific information to topic related groups. These LinkedIn accounts of project partners will serve as multipliers for sharing BioReCer-related content and news throughout their established networks and within suitable groups. To increase the project reach, additional suitable BioReCer related groups will be identified (e.g. bioeconomy, bio-based feedstocks, renewable materials, certification and labelling).

Project related content will further be shared by nova-Institute's company LinkedIn profile (ca. 4,100 followers), the account of nova-Institute's CEO Michael Carus (about 12,500 followers) as well as the accounts of other project partners (e.g. Cetaqua with ca 6,000 followers). The communication and dissemination team considers this strategy to be more effective than the creation, build-up and maintenance of a separate BioReCer LinkedIn community, which would be unlikely to have a stronger impact than the utilisation of already existing established partner networks.

All partners are instructed to tag the other project partners and the European Research Executive Agency (REA), and to use the analytics tool that LinkedIn offers for the evaluation of content reach and reader engagement which allows for an easy monitoring of audience figures. Using project related hashtags will increase the effectiveness of communication to relevant stakeholder groups.

A list of suitable hashtags will be provided to the consortium, e.g. **#BioReCer**, **#Certification**, **#EcoLabelling**, **#BioBased**, **#CircularBiomass** or **#BioFeedstock**.

A list of recent BioReCer related LinkedIn posts is provided below.

- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/leonardo-gaiani_biorecer-horizoneurope-activity-6991301383610118145-bjWO
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/giorgos-f-banias-158b0b5_horizoneurope-biorecer-santiagodecompostela-activity-6988606934023061504-5jDP
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/asta-partanen-34b2177_biorecer-biobased-biofeedstock-activity-6988496058204966913-cl_D
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/nova-institut-gmbh_making-the-most-of-sustainable-biomass-activity-6983402194934857728-F3Iq
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/adriano-ferrara-8bb27891_on-october-17-and-18-the-kick-off-meeting-activity-6988493743876157440-QaKb/
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/francesco-fatone-0662821_horizoneurope-activity-6987792061148086272-bxNP
- https://www.linkedin.com/posts/g%C3%BCI%C5%9Fah-y%C4%B1lan-b8890b65_biorecer-biorecer-biorecer-activity-6989167877496975360-5bf4
- <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6988849255306125312>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6975836918307516416>
- <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6982652461467500544>

Figure 7: Examples of BioReCer LinkedIn Postings

Twitter

The same strategy as for LinkedIn will apply to the use of the Social Media platform Twitter. Twitter allows the identification, selection and addressing of suitable target groups through the use of specific and related hashtags.

Rather than establishing a new BioReCer Twitter account, it is estimated to have more impact to gather project related and relevant hashtags that will highlight and suit the project objectives. BioReCer related postings will therefore include the project specific hashtag (**#BioReCer**), which will also be included in all physical and digital future communication materials. The hashtag has not been used prior and therefore offers great opportunity to be branded and established as a project-specific term as well as a high indexation for biomass focussed labelling and certification schemes on social media platforms in general. The hashtag can and will be used by all partner Twitter accounts as well as parties that are interested in being connected to the BioReCer project. To increase the project reach, the communication and dissemination team assembled a list of highly frequented project related hashtags such as **#BioReCer, #Certification, #EcoLabelling, #BioBased, #CircularBiomass or #BioFeedstock.**

All project partners will tag project partners and the European Research Executive Agency (REA), and retweet relevant, project-related tweets and hereby support the communication of project-generated content and news. Current Twitter figures of BioReCer partners include @novaInstitut with around 1,900 followers; @RenewableCNews with around 4,000 followers and @mkarus with 1,200 followers. Although Twitter itself shows lower interaction rates in comparison to other social media platforms, it is proved to significantly increase the recognition of posted content on other channels such as LinkedIn, in Newsletters or website news (Dwiwidi et al. 2021).

In order to monitor the success and impact of twitter activities, the communication and dissemination team will use the service "Twitter Analytics" which offers precise information and figures on visitor impression and reader interaction rates of the specific post. The use of this analytics tool is therefore equally recommended to all project partners.

In order to introduce the BioReCer project to the public and inform about the project kick-off event, various partners published related Twitter posts:

- <https://twitter.com/novaInstitut/status/1582727649201254400>
- <https://twitter.com/novaInstitut/status/1570070083392704513>
- <https://twitter.com/BioSquat/status/1582323720152002561>
- <https://twitter.com/TeresaAlvarino/status/1581608017560100865>
- https://twitter.com/Cluster_Spring/status/1570046372035846144
- <https://twitter.com/activecitnet/status/1572215091512107008>
- <https://twitter.com/mtortosav/status/1569629255167778816>
- <https://twitter.com/CETAQUA/status/1582275532456341504>
- <https://twitter.com/CETAQUA/status/1582055890886479872>
- <https://twitter.com/TeresaAlvarino/status/1582297421169987585>
- <https://twitter.com/TeresaAlvarino/status/1582320476709584896>

- <https://twitter.com/activecitnet/status/1582283413083811840>
- <https://twitter.com/anfacoceopesca/status/1583398291399925764>
- https://twitter.com/biogroup_usc/status/1582283495615123457
- <https://twitter.com/CETAQUA/status/1582055882212642818>
- <https://twitter.com/davidpxcheco/status/1582299307759132673>
- <https://twitter.com/normeUNI/status/1571807169942536193>
- <https://twitter.com/VIAQUA/status/1582044662851698688>
- https://twitter.com/M_W_Schaeffer/status/1570039985625243648
- https://twitter.com/cretus_usc/status/1582311543496007681
- <https://twitter.com/normeUNI/status/1571806418105438214>
- <https://twitter.com/elagoradiario/status/1570389720105893889>
- https://twitter.com/Bit_RG/status/1496167488039628810
- <https://twitter.com/aguaresiduales/status/1571778735338037250>

Figure 8: Examples BioReCer Twitter Postings

Newsletter and Renewable Carbon News

nova-Institute as well as all other project partners will actively incorporate, communicate and disseminate BioReCer news via their specific company newsletters. BioReCer further offers a project newsletter. Interested parties can register and subscribe via the website. Being one of the leading institutes in the renewable carbon sector, nova-Institute reaches over 3,500 monthly newsletter subscribers that include all relevant stakeholder and target groups from industrial bodies, policy makers and authorities but also the scientific community.

nova-Institute further hosts the news platform **Renewable Carbon News** (<https://renewable-carbon.eu>) that focuses on renewable carbon and renewable material and reaches more than 300,000 monthly readers. All press releases and news will be published via both paths.

Project partners are instructed to share links and information on published newsletter articles with the consortium to enable share and further distribution among the partners' respective networks.

Examples of BioReCer related Renewable Carbon News Publications are listed below.

- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/biorecer-guidelines-to-strengthen-current-certification-schemes-for-bio-based-feedstock/>
- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/biorecer-leitlinien-zur-starkung-aktueller-zertifizierungssysteme-fur-biobasierte-rohstoffe/>
- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/making-the-most-of-sustainable-biomass-certification-schemes-and-labels-developed-in-new-eu-research-projects/>
- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/nachhaltige-biomasse-optimal-nutzen-neue-eu-forschungsprojekte-entwickeln-zertifizierungssysteme-und-labels/>

BIORECER – Guidelines to strengthen current certification schemes for bio-based feedstock

New Horizon Europe research project BIORECER aims to ensure the best possible environmental performance and traceability of biological feedstock

Starting in September 2022, the new HORIZON Europe research project BIORECER aims to ensure the best possible environmental performance and traceability of biological feedstock used by bio-based industries. BIORECER will also assess the impact of current and adapted certification schemes on consumers and bio-based industry stakeholders along with their acceptance of new bio-value chains from biological feedstocks, including residual feedstock and waste.

Find out [more](#).

Figure 9: Example BioReCer Newsletter Article

Figure 10: BioReCer Article in the Renewable Carbon News

Press Releases

The press releases will communicate intermediate results, important milestones and extraordinary achievements to key media actors and will also be made available on the project website. nova-Institute provides a network of more than 1,800 press contacts, which will be effectively used in order to maximise project reach and impact. The press activities will include at least three press releases, summarising the project results and achievements. The project partners will distribute these press releases through their established media networks as well as through nova-Institute's own media platform and channels. Press releases and newsletters contributions cover task **T8.3.6** of the BioReCer project. Throughout the project duration, BioReCer will publish at least four press releases in English, which whenever possible will be translated into more languages and made available to targeted audiences.

Two press releases to introduce the project to the public and inform about the project start were published by nova-Institute, Cetaqua and several other project partners and were made available through various channels in different languages in the first project weeks. A list of published press releases is presented below:

- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/BIORECER-guidelines-to-strengthen-current-certification-schemes-for-bio-based-feedstock/>
- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/BIORECER-leitlinien-zur-starkung-aktueller-zertifizierungssysteme-fur-biobasierte-rohstoffe/>
- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/making-the-most-of-sustainable-biomass-certification-schemes-and-labels-developed-in-new-eu-research-projects/>
- <https://renewable-carbon.eu/news/nachhaltige-biomasse-optimal-nutzen-neue-eu-forschungsprojekte-entwickeln-zertifizierungssysteme-und-labels/>
- <https://beopen.openaire.eu/search/project>
- <https://www.bioeconomy-in-transition.eu/three-new-research-projects/>
- <https://www.industryintel.com/bioeconomy/news/two-new-horizon-europe-projects-star4bbs-and-BIORECER-focus-on-development-of-innovative-certification-schemes-labels-for-bio-based-feedstock-aim-is-to-address-urgent-need-for-harmonization-of-schemes-increase-transparency-of-global-and-eu-trade-flows-157822417488>
- <https://www.meo-carbon.com>
- <https://www.aguasresiduales.info/revista/noticias/el-proyecto-BIORECER-fomentara-el-uso-de-materias--RNMz9>

Project Video

In order to introduce the BioReCer project and communicate project related objectives and results to the public and interested stakeholder groups in a simplified and visualised form, a project video will be produced by the end of month 18, which equals Deliverable **D8.4** and is also part of task **T8.3.3**. The project video will offer an overview of the project structure and defined project objectives and impacts in an engaging form. Due to the simplified presentation of scientific and technological information it will allow the easy

communication and dissemination of project content to a broad audience. The video will further be implemented into the project website (<https://biorecer.eu>) and made available via nova-Institute`s YouTube channel. All project partners will support the sharing and distribution of the video through the individual networks and media channels.

Horizon Europe (HEU) Instruments

In order to introduce and spread the generated knowledge and instruments, BioReCer will also actively include and utilise the pathways provided by the European Commission. This includes the publication of all deliverables and publications on the project EU-CORDIS site, but also technology boosting instruments like the Horizon Results Platform, The Horizon Europe Innovation Radar and the Horizon Magazine. Whenever possible, Horizon Europe and associated organs will be informed and actively involved in communication and dissemination measures through direct messages or social media related tags, in order to utilise their wide reach and broad network.

Synergies with Other Projects

BioReCer acknowledges the importance of knowledge sharing and collaboration. All project partners will therefore actively utilise synergies with other related projects and their established related networks. This includes other Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, e.g. 3-CO, Star4BBS, BioMonitor, that focus on certification and labelling schemes for bio-mass and bio-based feedstock. To promote related projects and increase joint impact, a subpage with sister projects will be created on the BioReCer website in the future. Joint efforts will further include suitable initiatives, e.g. the Renewable Carbon Initiative (RCI), which supports the development and implementation of renewable (including bio-based) carbon solutions with 55 members from industry and science, initiated and founded by nova-Institute.

2.3.2 Offline/ Hybrid Activities

Infographic

Infographics present an effective information tool, that allows to describe complex processes in a simplified, visualised and structured form. They hereby support the building awareness, and increase of engagement and understanding of the tackled topic.

The complex interconnection of the BioReCer work packages and working groups and related outcomes (i.e., BRIE-LL, BRSP, BIT and the four case studies) will therefore be represented visually in a plausible, easy to understand and appealing way. Infographics can be used both online (e.g., on the website, in presentations) and in offline communication material. The BioReCer infographic was created with input from the entire consortium. Should a fifth international case study be executed, NOVA will create an updated, amended version of the current infographic. The infographic is part of **T8.3.3**.

Material for offline Communication (e.g., Brochures, Flyers, Roll-Ups)

Besides online communication channels (e.g., project website, Twitter, LinkedIn) BioReCer will also incorporate material for offline communication. Required materials will be created and designed with contribution from the entire consortium. This includes roll-up banners, flyers, brochures, posters and at least two policy briefs targeting policy makers, industry and certification bodies and the scientific community. Physical promotion material can be distributed and displayed at exhibitions, trade fairs and conferences. Leaflets, roll-up banners, infographics and posters equal **T8.3.3** of the BioReCer project.

Figure 11: Draft BioReCer Brochure

Conferences, Exhibitions, Fairs and Seminars

The presentation of the BioReCer project at different events like conferences, fairs and science exhibitions and the attendance of events outside the project framework will enable an effective and broad exchange of know-how and experiences with professional target audiences. They further allow comprehensive dissemination of project outcomes, results and chosen methodologies. Conferences and in-person events will foster and establish direct contact with representatives of relevant communities, such as industry, science and policy, and hereby strengthen the BioReCer network. Activities of this sort relate to task **T8.2.2** and cover its related requirements.

The consortium will actively promote BioReCer tools, applications, gathered project information or data through presenting and participating at numerous international conferences, trade fairs and exhibitions related to the bio-based industries, bio-based feedstocks, bio-resources, bio-based value chains, bio-based products and the targeted markets. Conducted research will be disseminated at least at six conferences in the related research fields. Events will be selected according to their relevance for the potential project impact and outcomes, while attendance and presentations will be executed by all project partners.

Industrial and academic partners will use exhibition event booths at national and international level to promote BioReCer tools and developments to industry, policy makers, certification bodies, end-users (e.g., users of bio-based feedstock) and the broader society. Whenever possible, all partners will include BioReCer in their general communication and dissemination activities on relevant conferences and events.

The nova-Institute organises four conferences per year and has many years of experience in organisation and attendance of trade events (one of them being the Renewable Materials Conference), as do the other project partners, who will all utilise their broad professional network.

A list of relevant project related industry and academic events will be provided by NOVA and steadily updated within the Communication and Dissemination Plan in coordination with the project coordinator and partners and shared among all participants. BioReCer will be presented at least 6 suitable conferences and at least 4 trade fairs.

Possible BioReCer events include:

Table 5: Upcoming Events and Conferences

Date	Title	Place	Link
14-15 February 2023	CLIB International Conference	Düsseldorf, Germany	https://www.clib-cluster.de/en/veranstaltung/club-international-conference-cic2023/
28.Feb – 02. March 2023	International Biomass Conference and Expo	Atlanta, USA	https://2023-ibce.bbiconferences.com/ema/DisplayPage.aspx
07-08 March 2023	BIO-raffiniert XII	Oberhausen, Germany	https://www.umsicht.fraunhofer.de/en/events-trade-fairs/2023/bio-raffiniert.html
08-09 March 2023	Cellulose Fibres Conference 2023	Köln, Germany	https://cellulose-fibres.eu
29-30 March 2023	International Conference on Circular Economy and Bioeconomy ICCEB	Paris, France	https://waset.org/circular-economy-and-bioeconomy-conference-in-march-2023-in-paris

18-20 April 2023	Argus BioMass Conference	London, United Kingdom	https://www.argusmedia.com/en/conferences-events-listing/biomass
03-05 May 2023	International Conference on Bioeconomy and Sustainable Development	Rome, Italy	https://waset.org/bioeconomy-and-sustainable-development-conference-in-may-2023-in-rome
14-15 May 2023	Autarika – Green World Tour	Stuttgart, Germany	https://www.autarkia.info/green-world-tour-stuttgart/
23-25 May 2023	BIOKET	Trois-Rivières, Canada	https://bioket-2023.b2match.io
23-25 May 2023	Renewable Materials Conference 2023	Köln, Germany	https://renewable-materials.eu
4-5 July 2023	European Wastewater Management Conference & Exhibition	Manchester, UK	https://ewwmconference.com
05-09 June 2023	31th European Biomass Conference and Exhibition	Bologna, Italy	https://www.eubce.com
14-15 June 2023	BioEconomy Conference	Leuna, Germany	https://www.bioeconomy-conference.eu/en/
04-07 July 2023	Annual ICABR Conference	Buenos Aires, Argentina	https://icabr.net/icabr-2023/
03-04 August 2023	International Conference on Bioeconomy and Sustainable Development	Montreal, Canada	https://waset.org/bioeconomy-and-sustainable-development-conference-in-august-2023-in-montreal
24-25 August 2023	The 4th World Conference on Waste Management 2023	Virtual	https://wastemanagementconferences.com/
21- 22 Septem ber 2023	International Conference on Agriculture	Jakarta, Indonesia	https://agroconference.com
12-14 Novem ber 2023	AFCC Global Biobased Economy 2023	Washington D.C., USA	https://www.altfuelchem.org
16 Novem ber 2023	Global Bioeconomy Summit	online	https://www.agro-chemistry.com/agenda/global-bioeconomy-summit/
19-20 Septem ber 2024	Fish Waste for Profit	Reykjavik, Iceland	https://www.worldfishing.net/icefish-conference

(Stakeholder) Workshops and Training Actions

A key element of the BioReCer project is strong stakeholder involvement. To ensure developed criteria are aligned with stakeholder interests and anticipate requirements of future use, at least 6 BioReCer workshops with ca. 40 participants will be held within the frame of WP2, WP3 and WP4.

To validate the developed BioReCer tools amongst relevant stakeholder and user groups, comprehensive training actions and user testing sessions with bio-based industry stakeholders will be carried out within **T8.2.3**. These will actively support the development of stakeholder acceptance towards the created BioReCer solutions as well as an optimised uptake of these tools. Outcomes of these workshops will further influence the content of **D8.6** and **D8.8**.

Factsheets

Factsheets will summarise relevant information regarding the bio-based industries, certification and labelling schemes, their associated requirements and certification processes and information benefits to various stakeholder groups but also the broad public. Factsheets will be provided in printed layout form as well as digital versions.

Policy Briefs

BioReCer aims to use all generated knowledge to complement current certification schemes and develop and include new criteria for certifying biological resources' sustainability, origin, and traceability. It further will ensure their applicability at EU and global scale. To ensure sufficient transfer of this information into the political framework, at least two policy briefs will be created. These will include practical suggestions, recommendations and key-aspects to help policy-makers to deliver successful strategies and instruments for the promotion and update of sustainable management and use of biological resources on an EU level. Policy briefs will cover the deliverables **D8.6** (due in month 18) and **D8.8** (due in month 36).

2.3.3 Publications

The innovative findings and results of this project will be disseminated to other researchers via Open Access peer-reviewed papers. Throughout the project duration, project partners will publish at least 3 peer-reviewed scientific publications in high-impact scientific journals and 3 industrial publications in trade magazines using green or gold Open Access. Results will further be communicated through publications in popular non-scientific magazines targeting the (bio-based) industry, scientific community and young researchers as well as policy makers and the broad public. All project related publications will follow the Open Access guidelines of the European Commission and a FAIR science approach and will be made available through a free online repository and on the project website.

2.3.4 BioReCer Tools

The BioReCer project aims to design and develop a multidimensional framework to analyse and define the assessment of the environmental performance of biological resources and their traceability. This will be subsequently validated in 4 full bio-based European case studies (and eventually an international case study) and applicable to a wide range of bio-based value chains. The BioReCer project will therefore create and establish its own tools for the communication and use of generated scientific results and information to relevant stakeholder groups. These tools include a physical approach in the form of the **Biological Resources Stakeholders Platform (BRSP)**, to be developed in WP4, and a digital path in the form of the **BioReCer ICT tool (BIT)** which will be developed within WP5. Both instruments will amplify the scope of the project and utilise information and data gathered and validated through the **BioResources Innovation Ecosystem Living Lab (BRIE-LL)**.

The BRIE-LL will include certification bodies, biomass producers and bio-based industries as well as consumer agencies and organisations.

While the BRSP serves as an innovative tool for the mobilisation and networking through participatory group activities (workshops, networking and training capsules), BIT focuses on the testing and evaluation of several machine and deep learning algorithms, providing stakeholders with key information and increasing the social acceptance of bioproducts on new markets and contributing to a better consumption decision-making and optimised uptake of generated solutions.

Table 6: Communication and Dissemination Channels, Addressed Target Groups and KPIs

Dissemination and Communication Channels													
Target Group/ Stakeholder Group	Website	Social Media	Factsheets and Newsletters	Press Releases	Video	Policy Briefs	Offline Material	Conferenc es/ Fairs	Works hops/ Webin ars	Open Access Publication	BRIE-LL	BIT	BRSP
Bio-based Industry (Producers)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Bio-based Industry (Consumers)	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Waste(water) Treatment Sector	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Authorities and Policy Makers	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x		
Scientific Community	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x	x
Civil Society/ Consumer Agencies/ Media	x	x	x	x	x		x	x	x	x	x	x	x
KPI	Min. 100 views per months	Min. 20 postings with >500 views each	Min. 5 reaching >50 subscribers	Min. 4 in English	Ca. 2,000 views	Min. 2	>2,000 copies	Min. 6 int. events	Min. 6 with min 50 part.	Min. 3 scientific articles and 3 industrial articles	Min. 20 partners		Min. 4 workshops with at least 50 participants each
Achieved	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC	TBC

3 Open Access to Scientific Publications and Data

According to the GA all partners are obliged to follow the legal requirements on Open Access (OA) to scientific publications and the principles of the FAIR science approach. This applies to all projects funded within the framework of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe. In consequence, all beneficiaries must provide access to a machine-readable electronic copy of the published document version or a final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications.

Furthermore, each beneficiary must ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to the project's results.

The term **"Open Access" (OA)** refers to the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to any end-user and reusable. Here, the term 'access' includes not only basic elements – the right to read, download and print – but also the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl and mine.

Meanwhile the term "scientific" refers to all academic disciplines. In the context of research and innovation, 'scientific information' can represent:

- peer-reviewed scientific research articles (published in scholarly journals), or,
- research data (data underlying publications, curated data and/or raw data).

"Peer-reviewed" publications are those assessed by other qualified scholars and experts. A peer review is typically, though not exclusively, organised and initiated by the journal or publisher to which an article or manuscript is submitted. The dominant type of scientific publication is the journal article. Besides, all partners are also strongly encouraged to provide open access to other types of scientific publications. These include project results such as:

- Monographs
- Books and chapters
- Conference proceedings
- Grey literature (informally published written material not controlled by scientific publishers, e.g. reports).

Due to the bibliographic metadata requirement, open access allows an easier finding of publications and ensures the acknowledgement of provided EU funding. To ensure a structured and proper monitoring of Horizon 2020 and Horizon Europe projects, all published material must include information on EU funding as part of the bibliographic metadata. To monitor possible embargo periods, publications

must include the publication date and name the agreed embargo period. Therefore, the bibliographic metadata of the publication must follow a standard format and include all of the following information:

- Publication (author(s), title, date of publication, publication venue);
- Horizon Europe funding;
- Grant project name, acronym and number;
- Licensing terms;
- Persistent identifiers for the publication, the authors involved in the action and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant.
- Where applicable, the metadata must include persistent identifiers for any research output or any other tools and instruments needed to validate the conclusions of the publication.

The two Pathways of Open Access (Green and Gold)

After depositing publications each partner must ensure open access to those publications via a chosen repository. Beneficiaries can choose one of two main pathways to meet this requirement:

- **Self-archiving/'green' OA:** Beneficiaries can deposit the final peer-reviewed manuscript in a repository of their choice. They must ensure open access to the publication within a maximum of 6 months (12 months for publications in the social sciences and humanities). To provide support concerning compliance with Horizon 2020 embargo periods, the Commission offers a model amendment to publishing agreements which are often signed between authors and publishers. This model is not mandatory but reflects the obligations for the beneficiary under the H2020 and Horizon Europe grant agreements. It can be supplemented by further provisions agreed between the parties, provided they are compatible with the Grant Agreement. The Commission/Agency takes no responsibility for the use of this model.
- **Open access publishing/'gold' OA:** Researchers can also publish in open access journals or hybrid journals that both sell subscriptions and offer the option of making individual articles openly accessible. Monographs can also be published either on a purely open access basis or using a hybrid business model. 'Article processing charges' are eligible for reimbursement during the duration of the project under the file 'other costs'. 'Other costs' are defined in Article 6.2.D.3 of the Grant Agreement. As stated, articles and other scientific publications must also be made accessible through a repository upon publication. Costs of 'gold' open access publications incurred once the project is completed cannot be refunded from the project's budget.

Free Open Access journals

The scientific landscape covers opportunities for free of charge Open Access publishing venues. An overview of Open Access publishing venues without APCs (Article Processing Costs) can be found here: www.doaj.org.

Zenodo Community

In order to ensure Open Access to all project related publications and materials (publications, presentations, conference proceedings, flyers, brochures, scientific posters and other scientific schooling material) even after the project has ended, nova-Institute established a Zenodo Community. Zenodo is a free of charge online repository built and operated by CERN and OpenAIRE in order to ensure pathways to and participation in Open Science as well as FAIR research outputs. All research results and publications are stored safely for future use by the broad society in CERN's Data Centre for as long as CERN exists. All materials published up to this point in the project process will be added to this online group and linked to the project website. The approach simplifies the publication process and ensures that knowledge gained throughout the project remains accessible to the public and interested stakeholders even after the project ends.

Zenodo further allows an easy citation of scientific work by using a so-called Digital Object Identifier. The DOI identifies and links to an authoritative version of the publication. In all cases, the European Commission encourages authors to retain their copyright and grant adequate licenses to publishers. In this context, Creative Commons offers useful licensing solutions. This type of license offers a suitable legal tool for providing open access in its broadest sense.

The BioReCer Zenodo Community is accessible under the following Link <https://tinyurl.com/mtaejunm>.

It will remain updated throughout the duration of the project period as well as after the project has ended. Additionally, Zenodo will allow an easy transfer and integration of uploaded publications, data sets, scientific materials and research results to the EC Cordis page of the BioReCer project.

Figure 12: BioReCer Zenodo Community

Website

All project related publications and public deliverables will further be made available for download on the “deliverables and publications” section on the project website by linking the entry to the Zenodo Community.

Self-publishing

All partners can also use alternative solutions by publishing articles or scientific publications on the individual website of their entity or institution, within an own journal or alternatively choose similar options. Partners should take into consideration that once they are publishing in a journal, in most cases they lose the right to self-publish.

4 Funding Statement and Right and Obligation to use the EU Emblem

According to the Grant Agreement, EU emblems and funding statement (Figure 10; translated into local languages, where appropriate) must be displayed for all communication activities related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), all dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant. Apart from the emblem, no other visual identity or logo may be used to highlight the EU support. When displayed in association with other logos (e.g., of beneficiaries or sponsors), the EU emblem must be displayed as prominently and visibly as the other logos. More information, guidelines can be found here https://rea.ec.europa.eu/communicating-about-your-eu-funded-project_en#how-to-acknowledge-eu-funding while various forms of the EU logo are available here for various purposes https://european-union.europa.eu/principles-countries-history/symbols/european-flag_en.

Figure 13: European Flag (Emblem) and Funding Statement (in English)

We recommend using the following funding sentence:

"The BioReCer project receives funding from the Horizon Europe Framework Programme under grant agreement number 101060684."

In addition, as per **Article 17.3** of the GA, any communication and dissemination activity related to the action must indicate that it reflects only the author's view and that the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains. This disclaimer should be especially added to all public deliverables (translated into local languages where appropriate):

"Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them."

5 Monitoring and Evaluation of Communication and Dissemination Activities

In order to allow a seamless monitoring and evaluation of executed communication and dissemination actions and measures, BioReCer will establish suitable instruments and define related KPIs. The instruments chosen for monitoring are the subject of the presented chapter.

5.1 Tracking of Dissemination and Communication Activities

Throughout the project duration, all communication and dissemination activities have to be documented and reported to the European Commission via the EU Cordis portal of the BioReCer project. In order to ensure a seamless documentation and monitoring of all partner activities, nova-Institute created a so-called ECAS sheet. This term describes an MS Excel worksheet aiming to keep track of all communication and dissemination activities carried out by the project partners throughout the project duration. The sheet covers a variety of possible activities, e.g., conference participations, organisation of workshops, social media activities, press releases and various sorts of publications which are documented in a separate tab. It also estimates and monitors the audience numbers reached through these specific activities, divided in various relevant stakeholder groups. The assigning of stakeholder and audience groups will be based on their own individual information, surveys or estimations.

The document front tab contains a summarising tracking chart which offers an overview of all dissemination activities carried out to date, a specific chart for scientific publications and patents and audience groups reached to this point in time. All project partners are required to keep an accurate own documentation of the sheet, while all results will be combined in a final master sheet hosted by nova-Institute.

ECAS results will be collected every six months and serve as a basis for activity evaluation based on prior defined KPIs and listed communication goals.

Type of publication (choose from drop down menu)	Title (article/chapter)	Authors	Link	Year of publication	Open access type	Reference
Press Release	Catapa	El proyecto BIORECER fomentará el uso de medicina personalizada gracias a la optimización de los esquemas de certificación estandar.	https://www.ecas.eu/biorecer-entrevista	13.09.22		
Non-scientific and Non-Peer-Reviewed Publication (popularised publication)	Catapa	El proyecto BIORECER fomentará el uso de las biomasas y bioproductos	https://www.retema.es/actualidad/ed-proyecto-biorecer-fomentara-el-uso-de-las-biomasas-y-bioproductos	13.09.22		

Dissemination & Communication Activities for the BIORECER Project:											
Activity (select the activity from the drop-down list on the next tab)	Total No. of Activities	Place	Scientific community (Higher E., Resear.)	Industry	Civil Soci.	General Pub.	Policy Makers	Media	Investors	Customers	Other
Organisation of a Conference	0	Spain	3000	1500	500	100	50	50	10	10	0
Organisation of a Workshop	0	Spain	100	500	500	500	50	20	50	25	0
Press Release	1	Spain	250	2000	250	250	100	20	100	25	0
Non-scientific and Non-Peer-Reviewed Publication (popularised publication)	5	Spain	250	500	500	500	100	20	100	25	0
Exhibition	0										
Flyer	0										
Training	0										
Social Media	0										
Website	0										
Communication Campaign (e.g. Radio, TV)	0	Spain	250	1000	250	250	100	20	100	25	0
Participation in a Conference	0										
Participation in a Workshop	0										
Participation in an Event other than a Conference or a Workshop	0										
Video/Film	0										
Brokerage Event	0										
Pitch Event	0										
Trade Fair	0										
Participation in Activities Organized Jointly with other H2020 Projects	0										
Other (dissemination/communication activity)	0										
Scientific Community (Higher Education, Research)	4100										
Industry	6000										
Civil Society	2500										
General Public	2100										
Policy Makers	500										
Media	175										
Investors	460										
Customers	135										
Other	0										
Article in Journal	0										
Publication in Conference Proceedings/Workshop	0										
Books/Monographs	0										
Chapters in Books	0										
Thesis/Dissertation	0										
Other (publication)	0										

Figure 14: ECAS Tracking Sheet

This tracking tool is updated at least twice a year with the information provided by all participating project partners based on their dissemination and communication activities throughout the reporting period. It also provides a basis (a database) for the technical periodic reports as well as the final dissemination and exploitation report.

5.2 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

To evaluate the overall performance of executed communication and dissemination activities, suitable KPIs have been created, which are listed in table 6. Deviations from this ideal scenario will be monitored and intercepted by corrective measures whenever needed.

6 Executed Activities

This section will provide a full and detailed overview over executed past dissemination and communication activities throughout the project duration.

7 Conclusion

Providing a cohesive and comprehensive dissemination and communication strategy presented in this plan will ensure a cohesive internal and external presentation of the BioReCer project and at the same time maximise the project reach and generated impact on a social, economic, scientific but also environmental scale. This will be achieved through tailor-made instruments and channels addressing the specific target and stakeholder groups. To measure and monitor the success of the selected measures, suitable KPIs have been selected and introduced in the presented document.

Recent measures and activities have focused on introducing the BioReCer project and creating dissemination and communication materials and channels, such as a project identity, a project brochure and infographic but also a project website and related content and imagery.

8 List of Abbreviations

BioReCer	Biological Resources Certifications Schemes
BIT	BioReCer ICT-tool
BRIE-LL	BioReCer Innovation Ecosystem Living Lab
BRSP	BioResources Stakeholders Platform
CDP	Communication and Dissemination Plan
CERN	Conseil Européen pour la Recherche Nucléaire
C&D	Communication and Dissemination
D	Deliverable
DSS	Data Support System
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reuse
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
KER	Key Exploitation Results
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
OA	Open Access
PU	Public
SEN	Sensitive
T	Task
T&T	Tracking and Traceability
WP	Work Package
WTP	Willingness to Pay

9 References

Dwiwedi et al.; (2021), "Setting the future of digital and social media marketing research: Perspectives and research propositions"; in International Journal of Information Management Vol.59 August 2021 (<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0268401220308082>)

Annex A

BioReCer
Colours

Yellow	Green	Blue	Grey
CMYK 0 30 85 0	CMYK 75 0 100 0	CMYK 100 70 0 30	CMYK 25 0 0 55
RGB 250 183 40	RGB 37 166 45	RGB 0 60 124	RGB 112 134 143
Hex #fab728	Hex #25a62d	Hex #003c7c	Hex #70868f

BioReCer colour codes and format templates

	<p>Yellow CMYK: 0/30/85/0 RGB: 250/183/40 HEX: #fab728</p>
	<p>Green CMYK: 75/0/100/0 RGB: 37/166/45 HEX: #25a62d</p>
	<p>Blue CMYK: 100/70/0/30 RGB: 0/60/124 HEX: #003c7c</p>
	<p>Grey CMYK: 25/0/0/55 RGB: 112/134/143 HEX: #70868f</p>

BioReCer Colors	
#000000 - Text/Background - dark 1	
#ffffff - Text/Background - bright 1	
#003570 - Text/Background - dark 2	
#e0e0e0 - Text/Hintergrund - bright 2	
#fab728- Accent 1	
#25a62d- Accent 2	
#003c7c- Accent 3	
#70868f- Accent 4	
#25a62d- Accent 5	
#25a62d- Accent 6	
#03c7c- Link	
#954F72 - visited Link	

Formatierung löschen
BRC_Cover_category 10 pt
BRC_Cover_Subtitle
BRC_Cover_Subtitle_2
BRC_Cover_table_8 pt
BRC_Dellverable reference number
BRC_Head Executive Summary,Annex
BRC_Header contents
BRC_Project funding no
BRC_standard
BRC_table content
BRC_table head
BRC_Title1
Standard
table_title_content
WP_standard
1 Überschrift 1,BRC_Header 1
1.1 Überschrift 2,BRC_Header 2
1.1.1 Überschrift 3,BRC_Header 3
Überschrift 4
Fett,BRC_bold_blue 10pt
Beschriftung,BRC_labeling
Verzeichnis 1,BRC_List of contents 1
Verzeichnis 2,BRC_List of contents 2
Verzeichnis 3,BRC_List of contents 3
Abbildungsverzeichnis,BRC_List of figures
Fußzelle,BRC_footer
Hyperlink
Kopfzelle,BRC_header

Figure 15: Important Styles and Format Templates